

Utilizing Causal Learning for Cognitive Management of 6G Networks

Mehmet Karaca¹, Jishnu Sadasivan², Ahmet Cihat Baktir¹, Alexandros Palaios³, András Zahemszky⁴

¹Ericsson Research, Turkey.

²Ericsson Research, India.

³Ericsson Research, Germany.

⁴Ericsson Research, Sweden.

firstname.lastname@ericsson.com

Abstract—In this paper, we study the use of causal reasoning for a cognitive network where we investigate causal discovery and its use in the context of 6G. The fundamental requirement in causal inference is to discover the causal relation among variables in a complex system (such as among a number of network KPIs). Once such causal relations are correctly captured, the cognitive capability of a network can significantly be increased by having the ability of causal and counterfactual reasoning. We envision that this can additionally bolster the trust and transparency to such cognitive system. First, we attempt to discover a causal graph that represents the causal relation in a networking setup. By applying the state-of-the-art causal discovery algorithms that include both constraint and score-based methods, we aim at uncovering which network KPIs and actions are causally impacting each other. It is observed that the causal discovery algorithms are able to capture the causal relations between the network KPIs and actions, reasonably well. Then, we give a use-case example within an autonomous network context, and evaluate the estimated causal graph with our realistic network emulator to predict the impact of an intervention on a network KPI. The preliminary results are promising and pave the way for more focused future studies that can support complex commercial networks in a scalable way.

Index Terms—Causal graph discovery, reasoning, prediction, intervention, digital twin, autonomous networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Towards to the aim of achieving faster, more reliable, and smarter wireless communication, cognitive 6G networks opens a new era in connectivity. As the successor to 5G, 6G goes beyond the limitation of the traditional wireless networks, promising to deliver exceptional performance and capabilities that are unmatched. At its core, cognitive 6G is not just about enhancing data speeds; it represents a holistic evolution that leverages an advanced network architecture with which the artificial intelligence natively integral part of it, and it targets to create a networking environment that adapts, learns, and optimizes itself in real-time [1]. This transformative technology promises to bring a multitude of applications, from augmented reality to autonomous systems, that will reshape industries, societies, and telco business [6].

This work was supported by The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) through the 1515 Frontier Research and Development Laboratories Support Program under Project 5169902, and has been partly funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe/JU SNS project Hexa-X-II (Grant Agreement no. 101095759).

It is expected that ML and AI will be the essential part of a 6G system. While machine learning excels at identifying correlations and patterns in the data, and making predictions based on data, a true cognitive system additionally should have the capability of uncovering the underlying mechanisms driving those correlations [2], [3]. This advanced capability is needed to not only predict/explain the outcomes but also intervene and manipulate these outcomes for a better-informed decision-making and optimization. In general, as an example, communication networks are complex systems that function through the collaboration of numerous components to deliver services to end users, and meet specific Service Level Agreements (SLAs). The quality of these services is influenced by various factors, making it a challenging yet crucial task to comprehend the impact of each parameter on the overall performance. However, directly manipulating individual factors to assess their effects is often unfeasible due to the considerable cost involved in network intervention. Consequently, it is preferable to embrace a formal approach in comprehending the role of different parameters and predicting how altering any of these factors will affect performance.

Causal inference, which learns the dependency structure among various networking variables, can allow us to ask “what if” questions and explore and analyze the potential hypothetical intervention on various network configurations or even on new policies and functions. Answering a “what if” type of question is more crucial for 6G network where the complexity and dynamicity of new services increase significantly and assessing the impact of a new network configuration is more important. One example question can be “what if we increase transmit power” or “what if we assign a new priority to service X?”. Although causal inference can offer several significant advantages over typical ML approaches, discovering the causal relations in a complex system is difficult in practice. There has been many causal discovery algorithms [4], [5], [7], [8], [10], [11] that can work with different assumptions and models. Since in real-world applications often these assumptions do not fit well, the applicability of these algorithms is challenged with more realistic assumptions and data. Therefore, it is important to understand how the assumptions fit well in networking domain under consideration, and which algorithm can work better with the characteristic of network data (i.e., different

Fig. 1. Example of a causal graph

noise distribution, time-series).

In this paper, we aim at answering these two questions: i- Is it possible to discover the causal graph representing the causal relations between different network KPIs and actions?; ii- Once the graph is estimated or given, how can we exploit and benefit the causal graph particularly from a 6G perspective? To answer the first question, we employ different state-of-art causal discovery algorithms and test their performance through our network emulator with realistic network traffic. The results indicate that the existing algorithms can capture important causal-relationships. For the second question, we give motivating examples on how a causal graph can help for the current research problem in an autonomous 6G network.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

In this section, we give a background information on causal graphs and also motivation on how we can benefit from causality for 6G networks.

A. Background on Causality

A causal graph (aka Causal Bayesian Graph) represents the variables in a given data set as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) [16]. A causal graph consists of nodes and directed edges, where a node represents a variable or component, and an edge from node A to B reveals that a change in A causes a change in B .

Figure 1 depicts an example for a causal graph, where there are five variables (i.e., nodes), X , Y , Z , W , T . An arrow (also called directed edge or link) indicates there is causal relation between a given two given nodes. For example, the arrow is pointing from X to Z means that X is a cause of Z or X is causing Z . For this example graph in Figure 1, there is also a relation between W and T but this relation is not causal. After analyzing data for W and T , this relation can be observed as one can expect some level of correlation between W and T . Importantly, there is significant difference between causality and correlation and in this example, W does not cause T (or vice versa) but there is correlation between W and T . This difference becomes very important when we do interventions on certain nodes to make a change on some certain nodes. For instance, if we want to change W , it will not help to change T although they can be highly correlated. To change W , we need to change X or Y that can change Z and W . To make this change possible, we need to know the causal relations (i.e., we need to discover the causal graph).

Another way to represent causal relation is to use a Structure Causal Model (SCM) [16]. With SCM, the variables are connected through a set of function. As an example, Z is a function of both X and Y , and we define it as follows:

$$Z := f(X, Y, n_z) \quad (1)$$

$:$ is used to denote that X and Y are direct cause of Z where $f(\cdot)$ is a function (can be modeled using a simple linear or a very complex non-linear function) and n_z denotes a random noise. Learning the function f can be treated as a regression problem, where we fit a function with the data of X , Y , and Z .

In our networking context, a node can be a networking or service KPI or a network configuration. For instance, based on the graph in Figure 1, X can be a network configuration such as a new priority level assigned to a service, transmit power, amount of resource allocated to a user or service, etc. Also, Z can be a network or service KPI such as throughput, latency, packet loss, Quality of Experience (QoE), etc. A KPI can be causally affected by some network configuration (i.e., allocated bandwidth) and some other uncontrollable network states such as cell load, channel condition and some other network KPIs (i.e., QoE is impacted by throughput).

Discovering the causal relations in a complex system is a fundamental problem, and to the best of our knowledge, there is no a single method that can discover the causal graph for any given system but there has been causal discovery algorithms which can be roughly divided into two categories as we next explain them briefly.

Constraint-based Algorithms: These types of algorithms rely on statistical independence tests. Notable algorithms in this category of algorithms include PC (Peter-Clark) [4], [5]. The PC algorithm consists of two stages: at the first stage a skeleton of the graph which contains undirected edges (i.e., there is a causal relation between X and Y , X - Y but the direction is not resolved yet) is found. At this stage, the graph is fully connected (every node is connected to every other node in the network). Then it applies unconditional independence test between two variables. For instance, if X and Y are tested to be independent the link between them is deleted. If these two variables are independent, then next we start with conditional independence test by conditioning on other variables in the network, and if we find a set of variables that make these two nodes independent then we remove the edge. Otherwise, we keep the edge. Once the skeleton is determined, next we orient the edge by using collider or V-structure that are used to discover the directions with the help of conditional Independence tests. More details can be found in [4].

Score-based Algorithms: Score-based techniques, on the other hand, operate by attributing a certain measure (i.e., score) of how effectively a graph aligns with the data. Elevated scores indicate a more favorable alignment, and a score-based methodology can be conceptualized as an optimization endeavor, where the objective is to search for the graph that attains the best score. Popular score based causal discovery

algorithms include GES (Greedy Equivalent Search) [7], [8], [9].

B. Motivation Behind Causality

Next, we give exemplary motivation for the usage and benefit of causal learning particularly for a cognitive network point of view.

Root-Cause Analysis Root-cause analysis seeks to identify the fundamental causes of problems rather than merely addressing their symptoms. By applying causal reasoning, the sequence of events can be traced and dependencies that led to an incident, enabling the prevention of recurrence by addressing the root causes directly. For instance, there can be many alarms that network operator encounter, many of those alarm can be highly correlated. Identifying the root-cause of an alarm can guide us to find the correct actions to fix the networking issue [15]. Also, it is likely with 6G that a new KPI can be introduced, and the expectation on this new KPI should be autonomously fulfilled. It is important for a network to decompose and understand that which existing KPIs are the main cause of the new KPI. Such as a new KPI can be impacted both throughput and packet loss.

Counterfactual Reasoning: Counterfactual reasoning is a cognitive process that can help us understand the alternate possibilities scenarios [3]. It involves constructing hypothetical situations in which events, actions, or conditions are imagined to have happened differently from what actually occurred. This process allows to explore the causal relationships between actions and outcomes, even in situations where those actions were not taken. In causal inference, counterfactual scenarios are used to estimate the effect of interventions by comparing the observed outcome with the hypothetical outcome that would have occurred had the intervention not taken place. As an example, a cognitive agent that aims to fix a networking issue proposed a new network configuration but the proposed action did not solve the issue. The agent can make counterfactual argument and stimulate an counterfactual scenario to understand how alternative network configuration would have solved the issue.

Explainable AI: Causality plays a pivotal role for explainable AI (XAI) by providing a structured framework for understanding and clarifying the decision-making processes of AI systems. In XAI, the goal is not only to generate accurate predictions but also to provide interpretable and comprehensible explanations for those predictions. Causality helps understand why a particular decision was made, by bringing the causal factors and relationships that influenced the outcome. Causal explanations enable us to grasp not just the "what" but also the "why" behind AI-generated insights, ultimately making AI systems more accessible and reliable [12].

Digital Twin: A digital twin is a virtual representation of a physical system or process, and it is used for simulation, analysis, and decision-making purposes. The role of a causal graph in the context of a digital twin is to represent and understand the causal relationships between various components

and factors within the system being simulated [13]. These causal relationships are actually the physical data generation process for networking KPIs. We can define the physical data generation process of a network KPI as how the KPI depends other factors that may include other KPIs, network states and configurations. For example, QoE can depend on throughput and also delay. In order to characterize and abstract the physical model of a network KPI, the causal parents of that KPI is needed. Once the parents are determined, it can be represented in a functional form and virtualized in a digital twin.

We note that we need to learn the causal relation (i.e., causal graph) to utilize all these benefits. Therefore, our main research problem in this paper is to discover the causal graph within our networking domain by employing the state of art causal discovery algorithms. As the performance of these algorithms can vary with the characteristics of data set, we evaluate them in realistic network emulator as we describe next.

III. EXPERIMENT SETUP

A. Network Emulator

In order to conduct experiments and validate ideas towards integrating causal learning into cognitive intent-based operations, we used an in-house network emulator. The network emulator consists of containerized entities including network functions, UEs, and application instances. These individual components are implemented as web servers providing a set of APIs enabling configuration management. Based on these capabilities, the set of actions that can be executed to reconfigure the network is as follows:

Priority: Changing the priority of a service instance that reconfigures how much resource a service can take.

MBR (Maximum Bit Rate): Changing the maximum throughput that can be achieved by a particular UE.

Propagation delay : It is a system parameter within the emulator and we change the propagation delay with adjusting this parameter. Consequently it changes the round trip time (RTT) between the video service and a video UE.

Air-bandwidth: It is the total system bandwidth that affects the maximum throughput that can be achieved by a UE.

We implemented two different service types hosted in the network emulator: (1) Conversational video and (2) Ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC). For the URLLC type service, the main KPIs defining the performance requirement are latency and reliability (i.e., packet loss). On the other hand, conversational video represents an Enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) type service that is not latency intolerant. Instead, for this kind of service type, there are Key quality indicators (KQIs) in addition to KPIs that formulate the experienced performance by the user. For this reason, we define QoE as the target KPI, which is based on both network and application layer measures. In addition to these service KPIs, we implemented relevant capabilities in the emulator to measure and expose throughput, which is assumed to have high correlation with the service KPIs.

B. Experiment Setup

We conduct the experiments with a single instance of each service type (conversational video or URLLC). For a particular setting, we run the emulator by taking arbitrary actions (e.g., change priority or MBR) to explore the state space and collect test data under different configurations. The exposed measurements are collected for every 5 seconds, and an arbitrary action is taken for every 100 seconds.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we provide the results on how we obtain causal graph, using the data obtained from the network emulator described in the previous section.

We consider two different scenarios:

Scenario 1: In this first scenario, we consider a conversation video service where the real video traffic is flowing from the server located at the central site to a UE. For this scenario, we configure both MBR and the propagation delay parameter, and we note that the RTT is only impacted by this propagation delay. We measure the following KPIs: throughput, RTT, and Quality of Experience (QoE). QoE is function of both throughput and the delay which, as our domain knowledge, are the actual causal parents of QoE. One expectation from the causal discovery algorithms is to find the causal links between throughput and QoE, and RTT and QoE. In the data set, for a given configuration (i.e., for a given MBR and the propagation delay), there are the average values of the KPIs (i.e., time-averaged throughput, QoE and RTT). In total, we have 500 data points in the set, where each data point represents a distinct network configuration (i.e., a unique MBR and the propagation delay) and corresponding average KPI values.

We randomly divide the total data set into smaller sets which each set contains %80 of the whole set, and we apply PC algorithm with these smaller sets to see how the algorithm behaves when the data changes. Next, the graphs show the edges that appear most frequently when found by the algorithm over different smaller sets. Figure 2 shows the causal graph that we obtain for scenario 1 with using PC algorithm. Since we randomly change MBR and the propagation delay, MBR and RTT changes independently and are not impacted by any other metrics, and they are the main causal parents (no incoming arrow to these variables and this is our domain knowledge). It is observed that PC algorithm correctly finds that these are the main parent nodes (not the child of any other node). In addition to the fact that MBR and the RTT are detected as the main causal parent they both impact the throughput, which is perfectly aligned with our domain knowledge. Also, PC algorithm correctly finds that there is a causal link between RTT and QoE and its direction is correct. Based on our domain knowledge throughput is impacting QoE, and PC algorithm also finds that there is link between throughput and QoE but it does not always point the correct direction. For the packet loss (PL), the algorithm finds that PL is impacting QoE but this edge is not consistent as it does not appear frequently.

Fig. 2. Causal Graph for Scenario 1 with PC

Fig. 3. Causal Graph for Scenario 1 with GES

It is important to highlight that the performance of PC algorithm may significantly vary with different conditional independence tests. In this paper, we employ Kernel-based Conditional Independence test (KCI) [18] with PC, which does not assume any specific functional form or distribution. Another point we need to highlight is that different data sets can still give different graphs where some edges may not appear or appear with a different direction. This may be attributed to the fact that we are estimating the graph with a finite amount of data and also PC algorithm's inherent property may estimate the graph which is a graph from the Markov equivalent class of the true graph [17]. We discuss these issues in detail in Section IV-B. Nevertheless, in general, PC algorithm can correctly find important causal relations among the KPIs in our emulator. Figure 3 shows the causal graph with GES algorithm for scenario 1. GES also correctly detects that MBR and RTT are the main causal parents. It also finds that RTT is causing both TH and QoE, which is aligned with our domain knowledge. It also suggests that other edges such as $RTT \rightarrow PL$ and now the edge between TH and PL is directed. This may be the fact that GES tries to give the best score for each variable in terms of prediction performance. Comparing to PC algorithm, we can see that both algorithms can find the important causal relations and they look consistent. We observe that GES is less conservative

Fig. 4. Causal Graph for Scenario 2 with GES for URLLC KPIs

in orienting the edge compared PC algorithm.

Scenario 2: In this scenario, we consider both video and URLLC services running together. The network configuration we can change for both services are MBR, Air-bandwidth (Airbwd) and also network priority level. For example, when the resource is limited, the URLLC service can get more bandwidth if its priority level is higher than the video. In addition to the KPIs of the video service, we have now also latency and packet loss KPIs for the URLLC service. Similar to Scenario 1, we randomly change the network configurations to collect the data. Specifically, we randomly change MBR, Airbwd, and the priority level of video and URLLC service and compute the average KPI values. Figure 4 shows the causal graph obtained using GES algorithm for the KPIs of the URLLC service. Similar to what we observe from scenario 1, some edges with GES are found more consistently depending on the set. For this scenario, we also exploit our domain knowledge. Figure 4-a shows the graph obtained with GES algorithm without using any domain knowledge. As Airbwd is independently varied, there should not be any arrow pointed to it. However, the GES algorithm finds an incorrect edge. Also, we know that priority should impact throughput as we use it to allocate different amount of resource to the service, and GES does not find it. Figure 4-b shows the graph obtained with GES algorithm with using a domain knowledge with the information that there should not be any edge pointed to Airbwd. Then with this knowledge we run GES again and from Figure 4-b we can see that now GES correctly finds that priority is impacting throughput. This can be a good indication pointing that even a small domain knowledge can improve the performance of a casual discovery algorithm by providing more correctly oriented edge. We will further investigate and explore the use of domain knowledge in our future studies.

A. Use-case example: Intervention Prediction

Once an estimated causal graph is obtained, one can predict the impact of an intervention on a given set of KPIs without actually making this intervention to the real network. We next evaluate the prediction performance of an intervention on QoE. Let us assume a cognitive autonomous network that we envision to see with 6G network. We can consider an intent-based automation, and intents are the high-level expectation of a service. For instance, a video intent can contain a set

Fig. 5. Target QoE varying over time

Fig. 6. Predicting the required throughput for a target QoE

of expectations or KPIs to be fulfilled. One of these KPIs can be QoE but the service provider may not know which networking KPIs must be met satisfactorily so that the QoE is fulfilled. When the QoE KPI is introduced, the network can observe and collect data as we do in our experimental setup. Then, it can run a causal discovery algorithm to discover which KPIs the direct cause of the QoE are. In an autonomous way, by utilizing the causal discovery algorithms, the network can identify that throughput and RTT are the direct cause of the QoE. Then, it can propose to take necessary actions to achieve the required throughput and RTT, and consequently the desired QoE. We evaluate such a scenario next, where our QoE target can change over time and we want to learn which KPIs must be adjusted and how much we should adjust them. By using the graph, we now know that throughput is one of the causal parent of QoE. Other causal parent of QoE is RTT. Without loss of generality we attempt to achieve the varying QoE target by adjusting the throughput. After identifying the causal parents of QoE, we make a linear regression on the QoE with its causal parents (both using throughput and RTT) and we make a series of prediction.

Figure 5 shows the time varying QoE target, and our aim is to use the causal graph and intervene on the throughput to achieve the QoE targets. By using the graph, we identify the parent of the QoE and then we need to estimate the value of intervention to be applied on the throughput to obtain the target QoE. Figure 6 depicts the predicted required throughput to achieve the QoE targets and the actual throughput values observed from the emulator (oracle). It is clear that we can closely track the required throughput, and in order to achieve the desired QoE we are able to make the suitable interventions. We note that once the graph is known, we can use it as a digital

twin of the network where the impact of the intervention is first evaluated. For instance, in this example we find which KPI (i.e., throughput) can be adjusted and then we learn how much we should change it. Once the required throughput is calculated, the network operator can keep using the causal graph, and take the necessary action such as adjusting MBR to achieve the required throughput.

B. Discussion

It is important to note that PC and GES algorithms use only observational data and are able to uncover the graph up to its Markov equivalence class. More specifically, the algorithms can output graph with the correct data distribution but cannot guarantee to identify the exact and complete graph with all the edge in the correct direction [17]. It can be still possible to uncover the true graph by applying purposely designed interventions to the variables but this solution may not be applicable to every system as it may not be possible to change a variable purposely. For instance, it would be possible to find the correct causal relations in a networking system if we were able to intervene on different network KPIs. However, we are only allowed to adjust the network configurations to change those KPIs, and we cannot directly set a KPI to a some specific value. This fact reveals an important conclusion that relying on these algorithms cannot guarantee to find the fully correct graph. It is likely that some edge can remain uncertain in direction, and at this point we have emphasised the importance of our domain knowledge.

There are also causal discovery algorithms that are more suitable with time-series data such as PCMCI [14]. PCMCI algorithm estimates the causal graph from time-series data and it can be considered as the extensions of PC algorithm to the time-series case. This type of algorithm can require more strict causal-assumption which may not held in practice such as causal stationarity that indicates that the time series is dependent on past/lag values, and the level of lag does not change over time [14]. In this study, we also applied PCMCI to our time-series data, but we observed that the consistency of this algorithm can be poor. We conclude that this can be due to the realistic data and noise can affect the performance of this algorithm. We highlight that fact that the performance of causal discovery algorithm can greatly vary depending on realistic and synthetic data used in the comparison. As we have a realistic network emulator, the data and noise we generate is close to a realistic scenario where the noise distribution can be different from the one assumed for these type of algorithms (i.e., Gaussian) and also the data generation may not be stationary. Also, the algorithms with time-series data need a good time resolution (granularity). If the data collection interval is not frequent enough then the temporal relations cannot be captured by the PCMCI type algorithms.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have studied the investigation of causal graph discovery that tries to uncover the causal relations between different networking KPIs through a realistic network emulator. We

observe that causal discovery can be achieved up to some level by capturing the important causal relations. We think that this is a good starting point that we would like to further improve in our future work. We also need to stress the need for integrating domain knowledge as this can significantly enhance causal discovery algorithms. This can be a good way to first increase confidence in cognitive systems as they would be less likely to capture spurious relations. Moreover, we proposed an intervention prediction (using the causal structure) to achieve the target KPI, and we observe that the proposed formulation identifies the required intervention values closely with the actual required intervention values. In future, we would like to test the performance of these algorithms in a more complex scenario including more KPIs. We also plan to develop more robust discovery algorithms with time-series data and test the whole framework with data possibly coming from an operator.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Saad, M. Bennis, and M. Chen. A vision of 6g wireless systems: Applications, trends, technologies, and open research problems. *IEEE network*, 34(3):134–142, 2019
- [2] B. M. Lake, T. D. Ullman, J. B. Tenenbaum, and S. J. Gershman, “Building machines that learn and think like people,” *Behavioral and brain sciences*, vol. 40, 2017
- [3] J. Pearl, *Causality*. Cambridge university press, 2009.
- [4] P. Spirtes and C. Glymour, “An algorithm for fast recovery of sparse causal graphs,” *Social Science Computer Review*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 62–72, 1991.
- [5] P. L. Spirtes, C. Meek, and T. S. Richardson, “Causal inference in the presence of latent variables and selection bias,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1302.4983*, 2013.
- [6] C. Benzaid and T. Taleb, “AI-driven zero touch network and service management in 5g and beyond: Challenges and research directions,” *IEEE Network*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 186–194, 2020
- [7] D. M. Chickering, “Optimal structure identification with greedy search,” *Journal of machine learning research*, vol. 3, no. Nov, pp. 507–554, 2002.
- [8] P. Nandy, A. Hauser, and M. H. Maathuis, “High-dimensional consistency in score-based and hybrid structure learning,” *The Annals of Statistics*, vol. 46, no. 6A, pp. 3151–3183, 2018
- [9] I. Tsamardinos, L. E. Brown, and C. F. Aliferis, “The max-min hillclimbing bayesian network structure learning algorithm,” *Machine learning*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 31–78, 2006.
- [10] Y. Yu, J. Chen, T. Gao, and M. Yu, “Dag-gnn: Dag structure learning with graph neural networks,” in *36th International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2019*, 2019, pp. 12 395–12 406
- [11] S. Zhu, I. Ng, and Z. Chen, “Causal discovery with reinforcement learning,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.04477*, 2019
- [12] Y. Wu, G. Lin and J. Ge, “Knowledge-Powered Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Network Automation toward 6G,” in *IEEE Network*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 16–23, May/June 2022, doi: 10.1109/MNET.005.2100541.
- [13] Chakraborti, A., Vainio, H., Koskinen, K.T., Lammi, J. (2023). A Graph-Based Model Reduction Method for Digital Twins. *Machines*.
- [14] J. Runge, P. Nowack, M. Kretschmer, S. Flaxman and D. Sejdinovic, “Detecting and quantifying causal associations in large nonlinear time series datasets”, *Science Advances*, vol. 5, 2019.
- [15] G. Winchester, G. Parisi, R. Harper and L. Berthouze, “Accelerating Causal Inference Based RCA Using Prior Knowledge From Functional Connectivity Inference,” *2022 18th International Conference on Network and Service Management (CNSM)*, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2022, pp. 10–18, doi: 10.23919/CNSM55787.2022.9964900.
- [16] Pearl, J., Glymour, M., Jewell, N.P.: *Causal inference in statistics: A primer*. John Wiley & Sons (2016)
- [17] G. F. Cooper and C. Yoo, “Causal discovery from a mixture of experimental and observational data,” *arXiv:1301.6686*, 2013
- [18] K. Zhang, J. Peters, D. Janzing, and B. Schölkopf, “Kernel-based conditional independence test and application in causal discovery,” in *UAI*. AUAI Press, 2011, pp. 804–813